

WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND ITS INTEGRATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6026545>

N.F.MIRKHASILOVA

*National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek,
Faculty of Economics, Human Resource Management, 2nd year Master's
degree student*

Annotation: *The article analyzes the importance of one of the non-financial motivation types, called Work- life balance, shares some of the statistics about it and ultimately, gives recommendations on how to implement this incentive to practicum.*

Keywords: *human resources, work-life balance, happiness index, compassion fatigue, burnout, Time-off encouragement, flexible schedule, role stagnation.*

In this rapidly developing world, where human rights and their preferences have taken a primary position, a new term in management, which is becoming in the centre of attention, started to reveal its importance. The term «Work-life balance» is one of the essential tools in human resource management, to demonstrate the efficiency of workers and increase the happiness index. So, what does the term itself mean? In Cambridge dictionary it is described as the amount of time you spend doing your job, compared with the amount of time you spend with your family and doing things you enjoy.¹

Another definition by thehappinessindex.com draw an attention claims, that maintaining a healthy work-life balance is not only important for health and relationships, but it can also improve your employee's productivity, and ultimately performance.² When we are stressed and over-worked, we run the risk of jeopardizing more than just our social lives – our physical and mental health is in danger too. It's no secret that when we are overworked, tired or stressed – our health will suffer. A poor work-life balance can lead to a variety of symptoms that

¹<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/ru/.../work-life-balance>

²<https://thehappinessindex.com/employee-engagement/importance-of-work-life-balance/>

can affect our wellbeing. Therefore, there has been launched a serious public campaign promoting the sport and exercising for workers worldwide, in order to remain their efficiency during work hours. According to the statistics, physical activity contributes to fighting stress, depression, and exhaustion. Exercise and work productivity statistics offer additional proof that healthy employees are productive employees. Exercising before coming in for work not only increases productivity by 15% but also extends the duration of an employee's productivity peaks.³ Subsequently, by helping your people to find the perfect balance between work and home, you will increase their engagement levels.

One of the Hr web-pages work-life balance conceptualizes as the method which helps employees of an organization to balance their personal and professional lives. Work life balance encourages employees to divide their time on the basis on priorities and maintain a balance by devoting time to family, health, vacations etc. along with making a career, business travel etc. It is an important concept in the world of business as it helps to motivate the employees and increases their loyalty towards the company.⁴

Barbara Rubel (speaker, trainer and author) is a leading authority on compassion fatigue, burnout, vicarious trauma and in one of her articles about work-life balance, she defines the term as a concept that focuses on calculating time working with what you need to accomplish in your personal life, without sacrificing the quality of your job performance. It is achieved when organizations create flexible work arrangements for their employees. Work-life balance is a personal preference that helps you make the balancing act of work and home life more manageable.⁵

Observation of international statistics demonstrates astonishing facts about the balance between work and life and its effects on both personal and work life. Taking the USA as an example, 66% of full-time employees in America do not have work-life balance and 60% of employees blame their bosses for work-life imbalance. They spend less than 12 hours a week on leisure and personal care. It is a fact that Americans are hard-working people but US work life balance statistics show that although they spend more than 50 hours weekly at work, they only enjoy 11.4 hours of the week. In comparison with a country such as the Netherlands where the average employee dedicates 15.9 hours of their time to leisure and

³ <https://learninghub.phsa.ca/Learner/Home>

⁴ <https://www.mbaskool.com/business-concepts/human-resources-hr-terms/7045-work-life-balance.html>

⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/work-life-balance-barbara-rubel>

personal care, Americans fall behind. Out of the 38 countries included in the work life balance research, the USA, surprisingly, takes the 30th position. ⁶

People spend an average of 13 years and 2 months at work. Work life balance facts astonish with the data that in a typical 50-year job stint, an average human being spends 4,821 days in the workplace. If you add overtime to this, then it becomes 14 years and 4 months. What is more impressive is that when items such as work, sleep, eating, socializing, etc. are taken out of the equation, it turns out a person has only 8 years and 2 months to enjoy life. However, it doesn't necessarily mean that the workers demonstrate the highest level of productivity during their entire working hours. For instance, Mexico ranks as the country with the lowest productivity rate in the world. Although Mexicans are extremely hard-working and tend to work long hours, the productivity rate of the country, in general, is very low at \$18.5 GDP per hour.⁷ This is yet another proof that long working hours do not necessarily mean high productivity levels. In fact the average knowledge worker spends just over 5 hours a day on their computers alone. By itself, 5 hours of time on your device might seem like a non-issue. Unfortunately, those 5 hours aren't entirely productive. Editor of the RescueTime blog, Jory Mascay in one of their surveys found out that looking at how people spent their time in 2018, knowledge workers, on average, have just 2 hours and 48 minutes a day for productive tasks (or 14 hours and 8 minutes a week).⁸

⁶ <https://www.oecd.org>

⁷ <https://teamstage.io/productivity-statistics/>

⁸ <https://blog.rescuetime.com/work-life-balance-study-2019/>

Yet, there is still a room to improve and implement for both, employers and employees. Companies, taking their culture, beliefs and challenges into consideration, should come up with the solution of work-life imbalance. There are several ways to achieve the balance between work and life, such as following:

1. Time-off encouragement. A break from work will provide you with the chance to switch off and enjoy yourself, it is also a great opportunity to recuperate and recharge. Numerous studies show that vacations increase company productivity and reduce stress. The American Sociological Association compiled a report, which suggests that a larger number of vacations lead to a decline in the psychological distress of people.

2. Implementation of short breaks throughout the day. Companies should consider installing a games room where people can socialize and take their minds off work. Consider encouraging light exercise throughout the day and introducing walking meetings outside the office. Many major hot employers like Google and Apple, game rooms have become a way for companies to boost

employee engagement and attract potential talent.

3. Flexible schedules. One common and popular way that employers help employees achieve work-life balance is through flexible schedules. Instead of a strict 9am-5pm workday, employees have the flexibility to shift their schedules. Perhaps work 10am-6pm or 7am-3pm with little advanced scheduling or approval. Of course, there are downsides to this. Some argue that this approach simply shifts time units, and doesn't address a deeper need for quality time. Others have noticed that flextime, though attractive for recruitment, can lead to disadvantages for younger workers in the form of lower wages and role stagnation.

4. Prioritization of work. Often employees do not give priority to work and end up doing a lot of work at the last minute. Better planning can help employees save unnecessary time delays, which can be utilized by employees for personal work.

Conclusion

Balancing your professional and personal life can be challenging, but it's essential. Attitudes on work-life balance will continue to evolve. Flexible leaders can update or reinvent their workplace culture to try something new if employees report poor work-life balance. While maximizing employee productivity will always remain a constant goal, ensuring employees have the time they desire away from the office and enjoy their time spent in the office is the best way to retain talented employees and make them lifers.

REFERENCES:

1. <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/ru/.../work-life-balance>
2. <https://thehappinessindex.com/employee-engagement/importance-of-work-life-balance/>
3. <https://learninghub.phsa.ca/Learner/Home>
4. <https://www.mbaskool.com/business-concepts/human-resources-hr-terms/7045-work-life-balance.html>
5. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/work-life-balance-barbara-rubel>
6. <https://www.oecd.org>
7. <https://blog.rescuetime.com/work-life-balance-study-2019/>
8. <https://teamstage.io/productivity-statistics/>

